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Research Article

Mentoring In Medical Education: Impact On The Undergraduate Students

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mentoring Programs have been developed in several medical schools, but few studies have considered both the mentees' and mentors' perspective. **Purposes:** To explore mentees' and mentors' perceptions regarding their experience. **Methods:** Mentees and mentors at a medical school were invited to participate in an in-depth consultation including questions on satisfaction, difficulties, and perception about the mentoring program. It was a questionnaire based cross sectional study. **Results:** 67% of students (mentees) benefitted from mentoring. Most students (82.5%) preferred one to one mentoring. Only 68.6% had adequate contact with their mentor. The areas discussed during mentoring were mainly academic and other personal issues. Only few students (18%) stated to have no barriers in communicating with mentor, whereas other students stated time constraints (24%), lack of concern from mentor (15%) / commitment by students (6%) as barriers. Students suggested that chance should be given in selecting their own mentors, and address the above

barriers. Mentors' satisfaction and difficulties are strongly associated with students' involvement in the activity. Mentors believe changes observed in students were more related to life issues; for some mentors, there is no recognition or awareness of the program. However, most of the mentors acknowledged important changes in relation to themselves: as teachers, faculty members, and individuals. **Conclusion:** Attendance is crucial for both the mentoring relationship and strengthening of the program. Students involved in the activity motivate mentors in teaching and curriculum development, thereby creating a virtuous circle and benefiting undergraduate medical education as a whole.

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INTRODUCTION:

Mentoring is an essential tool for a successful career in medicine. Mentoring as a concept and practice for facilitating the health care professionals has evolved consistently since 1970's, introduced formally in medical education during late 1990's (Buddeberg-Fischer and Herta, 2006). As per the definition of Standing Committee on Postgraduate Medical [and Dental] Education (SCOPME), mentoring is 'A process whereby an experienced, highly regarded, empathetic person (the mentor) guides another (usually younger) individual (the mentee) in the development and re-examination of their own ideas, learning, and personal and professional development. The mentor, who often (but not necessarily) works in the same organization or field as the mentee, achieves this by listening or talking in confidence to the mentee'.

Training in humanities makes students more humane, including medical humanities in medical education (Ousager and Johanessen 2010; Pedersen 2010). Immediacy and personalized learning, the chief - learner relationship, has weakened in the framework of medical education. The prospects for eloquent communications have decreased among the enormous numbers of students in learning environments and disintegration of knowledge. The interactive relationship in medical schools in the present era is indicated by heavy competition among colleagues and distance between students and teachers (Woessner et. al., 1998; Bligh 1999). These consequences have reinvigorated the progress of Mentoring Programs in various medical schools (Woessner et. al., 2000; Malik, 2000; Murr, Miller, and Papadakis, 2002; Kalet, Krackov and Rey, 2002; Buddeberg-Fischer and Herta, 2006). Compassion, empathetic, philanthropy, and sympathy are some of the affective skills that are desirable in medical students and doctors. Due to strain and whims of our higher educational system all these characters are too often underdeveloped (Pedersen, 2010; Garmel, 2004; Frei et. al., 2010; Von der Borch et. al., 2011; Castaldelli et. al., 2012; Abdulghani et. al., 2011).

Unrealistic and extreme parental expectations, panic of getting ragged, humiliating teachers, solitude, extensive syllabus with nominal time for relaxation,

and a cloud of other issues makes the first year medical school difficult for most students (Behere et. al., 2011; Shah et al., 2010; Levinson, 1978; Daloz, 1999; Al-Dubai et. al., 2011). A sympathetic foundation will help students deal better with stress; mentoring programmes have been promoted with this prime objective (Garmel, 2004; Frei et. al., 2010; Von der Borch et. al., 2011; Castaldelli et. al., 2012)

A mentor, as a friend, helper, and a role model, can provide, as a more knowledgeable individual, to the professional and individual progression of a fresh medical student by delivering orientation and support (Levinson, 1978; Daloz, 1999). Mentoring includes a longstanding association between a senior person (mentor) who guides and supports a junior person (mentee); in this case, a medical student) during the complete phase of schooling and training. The objective of mentoring is to inspire the mentee to obtain his/her full potential by sharing information and experience, and providing emotional sustenance and encouragement. Mentoring has been found to escalate the academic achievement of students (Meinel et. al., 2011; Nakanjako et. al., 2011), this association benefits mentors as well, by way of increased output, gratification in the job, and self-satisfaction (Van Eps et. al., 2006; Cohen et. al., 2007; Flexman and Gelb, 2011). Some reports are available exhibiting the mentors' problems in the association with students and occasionally report that the mentors' observations of their own personal development (Frei, Stamm, and Buddeberg-Fischer, 2010). However a publication on the Mentoring program by Stenfors-Hayes et al., 2010 at the Karolinska Institute Teaching Hospital, analyzed from the mentors' point of view wherein, it was gratifying to be a mentor for most respondents. Mentoring improved their bond with the students and fostered reflection on their values and practices.

Mentoring system is in practice in most of the medical colleges around the world, but the analysis on how far this mentoring helped the students in achieving their targets in Saudi Arabia is not much known. Although it is acknowledged, that mentoring helps in successful career in medicine, the studies related to mentoring were hardly any from Abha, in

Aseer region of Saudi Arabia. Hence the present study was designed to evaluate the perception of students on mentoring program and its impact on them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Comprehensive qualitative questionnaires is an imperative tool for creating ironic and exhaustive data on issues like education, complex social and behavior by exploring the meaning of life experiences from the researchers' own viewpoint. Generally the questionnaires are poorly designed that include only a few issues. The investigator requires to be exposed to the perceptions and variables that arise instinctively, and provide the questionnaire to the participants for extracting meaning from the data (Britten, 1995; DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree 2006; Reeves, Lewin, and Zwarenstein 2006).

The present study was a questionnaire based cross sectional study, done at College of Medicine, King Khalid University, during June, 2018 to May 2019. The students studying MBBS course were anonymously and voluntarily involved in the study. These students had experienced the mentorship program during their course of MBBS period. The institute had a formal mentoring program for all MBBS undergraduate students (1st semester to 9th semester). A maximum of 20 students were distributed to each teacher. First week of every month was scheduled for a formal meeting between the mentors and the mentees. Apart from this, the students can meet their mentors whenever needed which is an informal meeting.

The questionnaire for the students included the following items:

1. How many mentoring sessions were intended by the program and how many have you attended?
2. How was the mentoring done?
 - (a) One to one
 - (b) Group mentoring
3. Which forms of communications are regularly used between mentors and mentees?
 - (a) Personal Meetings
 - (b) E-mail
 - (c) Phone
 - (d) Other
 - (e) WhattsApp
4. Was the quality of contact with your mentor adequate? Yes / No
5. If not why?
6. What are the barriers in communicating with the mentor?
 - (a) Tried but couldn't meet
 - (b) Time constraints
 - (c) Mentor was uninterested
 - (d) I did not commit to the program
 - (e) Any other specify
7. Do you think that mentoring is a good idea? Yes / No
8. The following topics were typically discussed between mentors and mentees?
 - Classes and difficulty in subject, attendance, results and marks, teaching, academic problems, academics and hostel facilities, personal problems, complaints, studies, hostel friends, tests, doubts, address, health care, sleeping habits, phone, always caring for just marks, any complaints, helped in difficulties, attendance and proxies, food, tips on learning, important questions, stress management, how to go about in exams, internal marks, mentor lacked concern, personal development.
9. Have you personally / academically benefitted from the relationship? Yes / No
10. If yes, please specify in which area (personally / academically)
11. Were you proactive during the mentoring sessions? Yes / No
12. What did you enjoy most about mentoring?
 - (a) Felt supported
 - (b) Mentor's concern
 - (c) Interaction

- (d) Allowed settling in
- (e) All problems addressed to a single person
- (f) Had someone to advice about the medical profession
- (g) Nothing

13. What skills did you develop as a result of the program?

- (a) Communication skills / listening
- (b) Reading / preparation for the exam
- (c) Writing (performance)
- (d) None, as there was no contact

14. Do you have any concerns about the program?

- a. Lack of commitment from both sides
- b. Lack of interaction
- c. Lack of time

15. Suggest how you would like to see the program enhanced?

- a. Allot a time / ensure meetings / regularize
- b. More commitment, more time, more interaction
- c. Have student mentors
- d. Mentors should make themselves easily available, show concern
- e. Both mentor and mentee should be equally involved
- f. Explain the importance of mentoring, as mentees feel hesitant to meet mentors / introduce formally
- g. Mentees choice in selecting their mentor

In addition to the students (Mentees) about 22 teachers (Mentors) were also involved in this study, to look into the perspective of the mentor's impression about the mentees and mentoring program in general. The mentors were interviewed in person in addition to a questionnaire prepared for their blind opinions. The personal interview and the secret / unidentified questionnaire for the teachers included the following items:

- (1) How much satisfied are you with the mentoring program of the institute – 0 to 5 scale (0 being awfully unsatisfied and 5 being extremely satisfied).

- (2) What do you think about the number of students allotted to you. - 0 to 5 scale (0 being very high number to handle; 1 is ok can manage; 2 being just enough; 3 being good enough; 4 is appreciable number and 5 exact number of students that a teacher can supervise).

- (3) How was the overall response of the students during the mentoring program - 0 to 5 scale.

- (4) What was the method of calling the students for mentoring sessions?

- (5) Did the students confirm the receipt of notice of the mentoring schedule?

- (6) How many announcements were made before being self-contained that the mentees will attend meeting?

- (7) How many instances were there when no student turned up at the mentoring platform?

- (8) How many mentoring sessions were intended during each semester and how many students attended each session?

- (9) How was the mentoring done?

- (a) One to one
- (b) Group mentoring

- (10) Which forms of communications are regularly used between mentors and mentees?

- (a) Personal Meetings
- (b) E-mail
- (c) Phone
- (d) Other
- (e) WhatsApp

- (11) Was the quality of contact with your mentees adequate? Yes / No

- (12) If not why?

- (13) Do you think that mentoring is a good idea? Yes / No

- (14) What skills were developed in the mentee as a result of the program?

- (a) Communication skills / listening
- (b) Reading / preparation for the exam
- (c) Writing (performance)
- (d) Improved scores

- (e) Better class attendance
 (f) None
- (15) Do you have any concerns about the program?
- (a) Lack of commitment from both sides
 (b) Lack of interaction
 (c) Lack of time
- (d) Suggest how you would like to see the program enhanced?
- a. Allot a time / ensure meetings / regularize
 b. More commitment, more time, more interaction
 c. Have student mentors
 d. Mentors should make themselves easily available, show concern
 e. Both mentor and mentee should be equally involved
 f. Explain the importance of mentoring, as mentees feel hesitant to meet mentors introduce formally
 g. Mentees choice in selecting their mentor
 h. Two or more mentors should be involved in the same group of mentees to enhance the mentoring program.

The questionnaire was prepared using survey monkey web site and the link forwarded to all the students by SMS, WhatsApp and email to fill-up the questionnaire online and also distributed paper copies to the students and adequate time was given to fill it. The questionnaire consists of the details of demography and questions to assess the perception of

the students about the mentoring program and how far they were benefitted from it. Open ended questions were also included in the questionnaire, like in which aspects they benefitted and any suggestions / changes they need in the present mentoring program. Ethical approval from the local ethical committee was obtained before distributing the questionnaire to the students and the purpose of the questionnaire was clearly explained to them.

The collected data was spread into Microsoft excel sheet 2010 version. The analysis was done and the results were expressed in percentages for categorical variables and mean for continuous variables.

RESULTS

The present study included 238 MBBS students, out of these 162 (68.07%) had responded and properly filled the questionnaire. A total of 106 (65.43%) Males and 56 (34.57%) Females participated in the study. The mean age of the students expressed as mean \pm SD was 21.64 ± 2.73 years.

Out of 10 mentoring sessions conducted, 33.33 % of students had attended all the sessions, whereas, 15.68 % have not attended any session. 34.52 % attended less than 5 sessions and 16.47 % attended more than 5 sessions. Average number of sessions attended by the students was 5.39 %.

Regarding the type of mentoring (One to one / Group / both) they were exposed to, majority of them (82.5 %) stated that they were exposed to one to one mentoring and 12.5% to group mentoring. The remaining students stated that they were exposed to both (Figure – 1).

Table. 1 : Barriers expressed by mentees in communicating with the mentor (Single option only)

Barrier	Number of students: N = 238 (%)
Tried but couldn't meet	18 (7.56)
Time constraints	24 (10.08)
Mentor was uninterested	15 (6.30)
I did not commit to the program	6 (2.52)
Was unaware of the program	67 (28.15)
Mentor allotted not known	66 (27.73)

Combination of the above reasons	24 (10.08)
No barriers	18 (7.56)

More than half of the students (67 %) stated that they were benefitted from the mentoring sessions, whereas the remaining students (33 %) were not. Among the benefitted students, 68 % stated it as personal, 14.8 % as academic and 17.2 % as personal and academic.

Most of the students (88.7 %) preferred to have mentoring through personal meeting and the remaining preferred through phone (2.3 %), email (1.4 %) and WattsApp (7.6 %). The quality of the contact with mentor was adequate by 88.6 % students and the rest (11.4 %) did not have adequate contact with mentor. 65.8% were proactive during the sessions.

The barriers in communicating with the mentor are given in table 1. Some students (22.6%) stated that they were no barriers in communicating with the mentor and some stated the combination of reasons.

Majority of the students (57.8%) opined that the goal of mentoring was to develop professionalism and support students in their personal growth. Some students had opted that to help in career development and few opined for the support in the research studies.

As regards to the mentors, the results of their personal interview and the questionnaire filled by them are summarized in table No. 2 and 3. The outcome of the study indicates that only 22.73 % of mentors were satisfied with the overall mentoring program. With respect to the number of students allotted to each mentor they were well contented. About 81.82 % of the mentors were disappointed by the response of the students for the mentoring program. Most of the students do not turn up for the meetings and they needed repeated reminders to attend the meeting. Some of the mentees turned up for the counseling after calling them over phone during the session.

Table. 2 : Barriers expressed by mentors in communicating with the mentees (Multiple options allowed)

Barrier	Number of teachers: N = 22 (%)
Difficulty in convincing the students to attend the meeting	22 (100)
Time constraints	11 (50)
Most of the Mentees were uninterested	22 (100)
Meetings arranged but none attended	20 (90.9)
Combination of the above reasons	22 (100)
No barriers	0 (0)

Table. 3: Showing the opinion of the teachers (N=22) regarding the mentoring program

Sl	Question	Response	Opinion by the mentors (%)
1	Satisfied with the mentoring program	Yes	5 (22.73)
		No	15 (68.18)
2	Adequate students allotted	Yes	20 (90.91)
		No	2 (9.09)
3	Overall response of the students	Good	4 (18.18)
		Bad	18 (81.82)
4	Preferred Type of Mentoring	One-to-one	19 (86.36)
		Group	3 (13.64)

5	Ideal mode of Mentoring (Multiple answers allowed)	Personal Meetings	22 (100.00)
		E-mail	7 (31.82)
		Phone	12 (54.55)
		WhattsApp	9(40.91)
		Other	0 (0.00)
6	Do you think that mentoring is a good idea	Yes	21 (95.45)
		No	1 (4.55)
7	Shall two or more mentors be involved in the same group of mentees to enhance the mentoring program.	Yes	16 (72.73)
		No	6 (27.27)
8	Skills developed in the mentee as a result of the program? (More than one answer)		
	a. Communication skills / listening		9 (40.91)
	b. Reading / preparation for the exam		11 (50.00)
	c. Writing (performance)		8 (36.36)
	d. Improved scores		13 (59.09)
	e. Better class attendance		15 (68.18)
	f. None		10 (45.45)
9	Drawbacks about the program (More than one answer)		
	a. Lack of commitment from both sides		10 (45.45)
	b. Lack of interaction		18 (81.82)
	c. Lack of time		12 (54.55)
	d. Lack of information with the students about the program		20 (90.91)
	e. Unplanned program guidelines		17 (77.27)
	f. Students were unaware about their allotted mentors		22 (100.00)

About 60% of the mentors formed a WhattsApp group including all their mentees and had frequent chatting over the app. Notice for the counseling sessions was given through this group. Some of the students

confirm the receipt of the notice and their willingness to attend where as others just neglected. About 3-4 announcements had to be made prior to conduct a successful meeting.

Figure – 1 : Showing the response from the students regarding their various problems during mentoring.

DISCUSSION

The term 'mentor' originates from the Greek classical story, The Odyssey, in which King Odysseus called upon a trusted friend named Mentor to act as the guide and advisor to his young son; Telemachus when he left for another country to fight a war. Mentoring is a Greek word, which means enduring. It is a long term relationship between the mentor and the mentee benefitting the mentor, mentee as well as the society by bringing out the best medical graduate who can take care of the community. Mentoring has shown to be essential for the acquisition of clinical and research skills, as well as career development.

According to Scott (2005), professional mentoring relationships are for the purpose of career guidance and assistance with interpersonal challenges. Scott identifies 5 dimensions of mentoring:

- 1) Mentoring relationship involves a more senior mentor and a less experienced mentee.
- 2) Mentoring consists of 3 emotions: emotional support, career assistance, and role modeling.
- 3) Both mentor and mentee will benefit from this process.
- 4) Successful mentorship requires personal interaction and exchange between the two parties.
- 5) A mentor has a more powerful position and broader experience within an organization.

Although mentoring in Medical schools is gaining popularity and is running successfully in the western universities, it is still lagging behind in the eastern part of the globe. As seen in our study we had a very poor response to our mentoring sessions. Meager number of students attended the mentoring sessions in our institute, which is negligible, though we had informed the students about the benefits and outcomes of the mentoring sessions. Hence, we feel that the mentors have increased responsibility in this region to impress the students who attend the mentoring sessions and bring out successful results among the students who attend the mentoring sessions regularly. The mentor should tame the mentee in such a manner that the student who regularly attends the mentoring sessions improves and tops his academic performance, psychologically sound, socially motivated, performs well in sports and other academic and extracellular activities. Additionally the students

who are regular in the contact with the mentor not only during the mentoring sessions but also in one-to-one contact, has a good rapport with other classmates and also with various teachers. Looking into the improvements in the students who are regular in touch with his mentor and exhibits good performance, will instigate more and more students to take up the mentoring activities.

Further in our mentoring program; one-to-one mentoring, considered to be more effective in motivating the students in improving their personality, failed to a great most probably due to distance and gap between the students and the teachers. This lacuna is basically due to the pupil feeling shy to approach his / her mentor, perhaps due to his fear of getting scolded by the teacher or losing marks in the exam if their weakness is exposed. In such a case the mentor should approach his mentees and increase friendly relationships so as to relieve the students from any type of fear from his / her mind.

The opinion of the mentee regarding mentoring program was not satisfactory as per the statistics of this questionnaire. This inadequacy in the overall success of the mentoring program at our institute can be attributed to flawed attitude of the mentors, probably due to lack of experience and familiarity dealing with the personal and academic issues faced by the mentees. Hence, the mentors need excessive training and know-how to tame students psychologically, emotionally and motivate them to take more and more mentoring sessions. The major constraint expressed by the students (Table 1) was lack of time to approach the teacher and for most of the occasions the mentor was not available for discussion with the mentee. Lower rate of achievement of this program in our institute can be attributed to the development of a negative impression about mentoring that it does not actually help develop professionalism and or support students in their personal growth. There is an urgent need that the students should be taken out of this dilemma and clear cut image be exhibited to them and create such an atmosphere in the campus that more and more students are attracted towards mentoring program.

In this manuscript we presented a closed-ended questionnaire study of 238, MBBS students'

perceptions of their experiences with mentors. Additionally, 22 mentors were also included in the study to have an opinion of the mentees from the mentors' point of view. The questionnaire was mostly multiple choice questions and a few open ended response opportunities. After analysis via Microsoft Excel, we describe responses to the various questions. Most students were mentored as one-on-one as opposed to groups and a little more than half of the students benefited from being mentored. In-person mentoring was preferred to telephone or electronic communications. Most students indicated that time constraints were a barrier to meeting with a mentor while professionalism was the top named goal. This was a single institution study that most likely has limited impact on theory or practice for a broad TLM (teaching/learning materials) audience due to the presence of mature mentoring programs in western medical schools. The major lacuna in our study which we observed is that the mentoring program in the eastern countries like Saudi Arabia is not on par with those in the western medical schools. Mentoring in Saudi Arabia has not been as popular as those in the UK and US. The mentors are not well trained and mentally prepared to take up the mentoring program. On the other hand the mentees (medical students) are also unaware of the benefits of such program and they have not seen their seniors benefit from mentorship.

Thus there is an urgent need to recruit such persons in these medical schools who are pioneers in mentoring the undergraduate medical students and simultaneously tame and develop a positive impression in the minds of the students regarding mentorship. The mentees should be trained by taking personal interviews. These will enhance the mentoring capacity of the mentors. As done in the western countries, the teachers in the medical schools in Saudi Arabia should be trained as was done by Patrícia Lacerda Bellodi, 2011. In their study an in-depth qualitative interviews was conducted four years after the program was launched, all 80 mentors of the Mentoring Program were interviewed using a qualitative methodology. The interviews involved open-ended questions and contained items exploring mentors' perceptions towards satisfaction with the mentoring program, difficulties, and changes resulting

from the program over time. The interviews were conducted with each mentor privately and lasted 30 to 90 minutes. Before each interview, the mentor's personal and professional data were verified (name, age, gender, and specialty) to establish rapport. Data on program participation was also confirmed (duration of the mentor's participation, number of meetings held with the students, and student attendance). The interview began with the question "Are you happy as a mentor? Why?" Mentors were then asked "When did you really feel like a mentor?" and "What kinds of difficulties have you faced as a mentor?" Mentors were asked whether they had noticed changes in the mentoring program, with the question "Have you noticed any changes in the students, yourself, or the medical school due to the Mentoring Program?" Answers were recorded during the interview (note-taking) and data were submitted to qualitative analysis. After a free-flowing reading of the collected material, answers with similar content were grouped into categories for the specific research questions (thematic analysis). The number of respondents was used as a measure of emphasis of the different categories. Mentors' quotes are used to illustrate and substantiate the findings.

Their report present that they interviewed 80 mentors of which, 56 were males and 24 females, accurately reflecting the overall gender breakdown in the medical school faculty. Age ranged from 30 to 60 years. The group included different medical specialties: internal medicine and subspecialties, surgery and specialties, pediatrics, psychiatry, orthopedics, gynecology-obstetrics, ophthalmology, othorhinolaryngology, anesthesiology, pathology, forensic medicine, and preventive medicine. As for academic status, the group included 6 full professors, 18 associate professors, 46 teachers with doctoral degrees, and 5 teachers with Master's degrees. Most of the mentors (74/80) had been in the program since the beginning in 2001, and while 6 had joined the group more recently. According to 51 mentors, student attendance over time was uneven; according to 10 mentors, the adherence rate had dropped, and only 5 mentors reported that student participation had increased. Student attendance was considered stable by 15 mentors. Despite of the reported differences in

attendance, 60 mentors considered the program excellent or good, and 74 stated that they intended to remain in the program. Such an interaction is a requirement in the eastern countries to improve mentoring programs. Preparation for mentoring should be undertaken by the host organization which oversees, administers and supports the mentoring program. Preparation for mentoring includes structuring the mentoring process, mentor selection and training, mentee briefing and creating a culture conducive for mentoring.

The selection of experienced mentors with proven track records in clinical mentoring improves mentoring experiences and outcomes. Mentoring outcomes are further enhanced by preparing mentors for their roles and responsibilities. Mentors in nearly 32% of mentoring programs in Germany and 63% of new US medical schools were received formal training. Mentoring training ranged from providing mentors with information packs describing the mentorship program to participation in workshops and seminars on mentoring, leadership and team building (Tan, 2018). Oelschlager et al. 2011 described monthly faculty development activities including sessions on mentoring, teaching clinical skills and professionalism and giving feedback to keep mentors up-to-date and supported.

Mentee preparation includes establishing clear mentoring goals with mentors and agreement upon the form and frequency of communication and support that will be provided. Mentee preparation is also enhanced through briefing and/or mentee training. Fornari et al., 2014 reported that 13 of the 14 US medical schools surveyed required mentees to be trained for participation in mentoring. Mentee training ranged from use of information packs to participation in intensive foundation courses carried out by the host organization. Structured mentoring programs span the preparatory, initiation and supportive phases of the mentoring process providing orientation programs, skills training and mentor training, preparing mentees for their mentoring experiences and enhancing a mentee's sense of autonomy, connectivity and advocacy. Structured programs also establish codes of conduct and standards of practice, define the roles and responsibilities of mentees and mentors and stipulate

the frequency, duration and form of mentoring meetings. Yet perhaps the most significant role of structured mentoring programs lies in its nurturing mentoring relationships, cultivating professional identities, role modeling and longitudinal relationships, fostering a mentoring culture and enhancing mentoring experiences for mentors and mentees through employ of a consistent approach to mentoring interactions and oversight.

The Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM) is a culturally non-specific, generic instrument; developed to analyze undergraduate educational environments in the health professions (Roff, 1997). DREEM has been found to be highly reliable in a variety of settings; with its help, institutions can identify shortcomings and formulate changes in curriculum. DREEM is a questionnaire with 50 items that assess five domains: students' perceptions of learning, 12 items, maximum score 48; students' perceptions of teachers, 11 items, maximum score 44; students' academic self-perception, 8 items, maximum score 32; students' perceptions of atmosphere, 12 items, maximum score 48; and students' social self-perception, 7 items, maximum score 28. Each item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 0-4 where 0= strongly disagree, 1= disagree, 2= unsure, 3= agree, and 4= strongly agree. There are nine negative items (items 4, 8, 9, 17, 25, 35, 39, 48, and 50), for which correction is made by reversing the scores; thus after correction, higher scores indicate disagreement with that item. Items with a mean score of ≥ 3.5 are true positive points; those with a mean of ≤ 2 are problem areas; scores in between these two limits indicate aspects of the environment that could be enhanced. The maximal global score for the questionnaire is 200, and the global score is interpreted as follows: 0-50 = very poor; 51-100 = many problems; 101-150 = more positive than negative; 151-200= excellent. Such DREEM questionnaires are required to be implemented during the upcoming studies on mentoring in India to enhance its acceptance among the medical schools.

At this platform let us discuss the difference in mentoring programs between the Western countries and Eastern countries especially in countries of the middle Asia like India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and

Saudi Arabia. In the western countries the mentor and the mentee remain like friends to each other and they are closely associated with one another. This reduces the gap between the teacher and the student. Now that the mentor and the mentee are close together the mentoring program can run smoothly and successfully. There will be minimum hindrances and problems encountering this issue, so mentoring will be easy and successful. Due to close association between the two; the mentee can discuss his or her personal, psychological, emotional and academic issues without any fear or hesitation. On the other hand the mentor can also solve the problems of his students efficiently by discussing the issue more intimately with the mentee; therefore the mentoring program is more successful in the western countries. Where as in countries like Saudi Arabia, there is no such close friendly and open association between the teacher and the student. The reasons for this distance between the two are many; to quote a few the cultural atmospheres in these countries is such that most of the students are afraid of their teachers and thus fear to approach their mentor. All the students may not be scared of the teacher instead some of the student has a very high respect for their teacher. Teaching profession is presumed to be the most noble among all the professionals in these countries which cannot be compared with any other country. Owing to this perception in the minds of the students, they keep a distance with their teachers fearing that they may misbehave with their teachers in the event of their being very free and liberal with their teachers. This criterion is a major drawback in the implementation of a successful mentoring program in the Eastern countries. In fact most of the colleges or organization in Saudi Arabia does not have any mentoring programs in their establishment. This scenario is not only in medical schools whereas all other technical institutes are lagging behind in taking up the mentoring programs. Hence it is high time that mentoring be popularized in as many institutes as possible and train the mentors such that the program is successful to a great extent and this will propagate with other institutes and slowly all the institutes will have good mentoring programs running. On the other hand it is also important to motivate students to take

active part in these mentoring programs. Active involvement of both the mentor and the mentee is very important for the success of mentoring program on par with the western countries.

Future investigation should test theoretical understanding of phenomena in medical practice and education. The objective of forthcoming Investigations should be to extend theory, which is a conceptual description or explanation of a phenomenon, and not a practical problem or gap, by revealing causal relationships and specifying how/when they hold. There is a need for new theoretical understanding enabled by the more such investigations related to mentoring programs.

To summarise, this paper pronounces our initial understanding of formal mentoring program for medical students. We believe that mentoring should be an important part of medical education. The determination required is very less, as it is not challenging for dedicated teacher and student mentors to find time for their mentees. Notably, there is advantage for both mentees and mentors; further trust and bonding among teachers and students increase. Mentees with operative mentors as role models will imbibe their qualities and, in turn, be good mentors, and thus propagate the cycle. Contingent on the needs and traditional understandings, each college can be exhilarated to indulge in its own mentoring program. The outcome, not the process must be the main motive of the program. Future work could focus on nurturing and sustaining philanthropic attitudes in medical students and faculty using mentoring and the medical humanities.

CONCLUSION:

Mentoring is an important tool in career progression of a medical student. A well planned and goal oriented mentoring program benefits not only the mentees but also the mentors. Strategies should be planned, especially in the developing countries to motivate the students and the teacher equally for the success of such programs.

REFERENCES

1. Abdulghani H.M., AlKanhah A.A., Mahmoud E.S., Ponnampuruma G.G., Alfaris E.A. 2011.

- Stress and its effects on medical students: a cross-sectional study at a college of medicine in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition* 29 (5): 516-22.
2. Al-Dubai S.A., Al-Naggar R.A., Alshagga M.A., Rampal K.G. 2011. Stress and coping strategies of students in a medical faculty in Malaysia. *Malaysian Journal of Medical Sciences* 18 (3): 57-64.
 3. Behere S.P., Yadav R., Behere P.B. 2011. A comparative study of stress among students of medicine, engineering, and nursing. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine* 33 (2): 145-148.
 4. Bligh J. 1999. Mentoring: an invisible support network. *Medical Education* 33: 2-3.
 5. Britten N. 1995. Qualitative Research: Qualitative interviews in medical research. *British Medical Journal* 311: 251-3
 6. Buddeberg-Fischer B, Herta K.D. 2006. Formal mentoring programs in medicine – a review of the Medline literature. *Medical Teaching* 28 (3): 248-257.
 7. Castaldelli-Maia J.M., Martins S.S., Bhugra D., Machado M.P., Andrade A.G., Alexandrino-Silva C., Baldassin S., De Toledo Ferraz Alves T.C. 2012. Does ragging play a role in medical student depression - cause or effect? *Journal of Affective Disorders* 139 (3): 291-7. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2012.02.003.
 8. Cohen M.S., Jacobs J.P., Quintessenza J.A., Chai P.J., Lindberg H.L., Dickey J., Ungerleider R.M. 2007. Mentorship, learning curves, and balance. *Cardiology in the Young* 17 (2): 164-74.
 9. Daloz L.A. 1999. *Mentor: Guiding the Journey of Adult Learners*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Higher and Adult Education Series.
 10. DiCicco-Bloom B., Crabtree B.F. 2006. The qualitative research interview. *Medical Education* 40: 314-21.
 11. Flexman A.M., Gelb A.W. 2011. Mentorship in anesthesia. *Current Opinion in Anesthesiology* 24 (6): 676-81. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACO.0b013e32834c1659>
 12. Fornari A., Murray T. S., Menzin A. W., Woo V. A., Clifton M., Lombardi M. 2014. Mentoring program design and implementation in new medical schools. *Medical Education Online* 19 : 24570. <https://doi.org/10.3402/meo.v19.24570>
 13. Frei E., Stamm M., Buddeberg-Fischer B. 2010. Mentoring programs for medical students -a review of the PubMed literature 2000-2008. *British Medical College Medical Education* 30 (10): 32.
 14. Garmel G.M. 2004. Mentoring medical students in academic emergency medicine. *Academic Emergency Medicine* 11(12): 1351-1357.
 15. Kalet A., Krackov S., Rey M. 2002. Mentoring for a new era. *Academic Medicine* 77: 1171-1172.
 16. Levinson, D.J. 1978. *The Seasons of a Man's Life*. New York: Ballantine Books.
 17. Malik S. 2000. Students, mentors and relationships: the ingredients of a successful student support for medical students in Germany, Switzerland and Austria. *Medical Education* 34: 480-482.
 18. Meinel F.G., Dimitriadis K., Von Der Borch P., Stormann S., Niedermaier S., Fischer M.R. 2011. More mentoring needed? A cross-sectional study of mentoring programs for medical students in Germany. *British Medical College Medical Education* 11(1): 68. doi: 10.1186/1472-6920-11-68.
 19. Murr A.H., Miller C., Papadakis M. 2002. Mentorship through advisory colleges. *Academic Medicine* 77: 1172-3.
 20. Nakanjako D., Byakika-Kibwika P., Kintu K., Aizire J., Nakwagala F., Luzige S., Namisi C., Mayanja-Kizza H., Kanya M.R. 2011. Mentorship needs at academic institutions in resource-limited settings: a survey at Makerere University college of Health

- Sciences. *British Medical College Medical Education* 29(11): 53.
21. Oelschlager A. M., Smith S., Tamura G., Carline J. Dobie S. 2011. Where do medical students turn? The role of the assigned mentor in the fabric of support during medical school. *Teaching and Learning in Medicine* 23(2) : 112–117.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10401334.2011.561664>.
 22. Ousager J., Johanessen H. 2010 Humanities in undergraduate medical education: a literature review. *Academic Medicine* 85(6): 988-98.
 23. Patrícia Lacerda Bellodi. 2011. Mentors, Students, and the Undergraduate Medical Course: A Virtuous Circle. *Revista Brasileira De Educação Médica* 35 (3): 382-388
 24. Pedersen R. 2010. Empathy development in medical education--a critical review. *Medical Teaching* 32(7): 593-600.
 25. Reeves S., Lewin S., Zwarenstein M. 2006. Using qualitative interviews within medical education research: why we must raise the 'quality bar'. *Medical Education* 40: 291-292.
 26. Roff S., McAleer S., Harden R.M., Al-Qahtani M., Ahmed A.U., Deza H., Groenen G., Primparyon P. 1997.b Development and validation of the Dundee Ready Education Environment Measure (DREEM). *Medical Teaching* 19: 295-299.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/01421599709034208>
 27. Scott Elaine S. 2005 Peer-to-Peer Mentoring: Teaching Collegiality. *Nurse Educator* 30(2): 52–56
 28. Shah M., Hasan S., Malik S., Sreeramareddy C.T. 2010. Perceived stress, sources and severity of stress among medical undergraduates in a Pakistani medical school. *British Medical College Medical Education* 15 (10): 2.
 29. Stenfors-Hayes T., Kalén S., Hult H., Dahlgren L.O., Hindbeck H., Ponzer S. 2010. Being a mentor for undergraduate medical students enhances personal and professional development. *Medical Teaching* 32: 148-153.
 30. Tan Y.S., Teo S.W.A., Pei Y., Sng J.H., Yap H.W., Toh Y.P., Krishna L.K.R. 2018. A framework for mentoring of medical students: thematic analysis of mentoring programmes between 2000 and 2015. *Advances in Health Sciences Education - Theory and Practice* 23(4): 671-697. doi: 10.1007/s10459-018-9821-6.
 31. Van Eps M.A., Cooke M., Creedy D.K., Walker R. 2006. Student evaluations of a year-long mentorship program: a quality improvement initiative. *Nurse Education Today* 26(6): 519-524.
 32. Von der Borch P., Dimitriadis K., Störmann S., Meinel F.G., Moder S., Reincke M., Tekian A., Fischer M.R. 2011. A novel large-scale mentoring program for medical students based on a quantitative and qualitative needs analysis. *Germany Medical School's Zeitschrift für Medizinische Ausbildung* 28(2): 26.
 33. Woessner R., Honold M., Stehle I., Stehr S., Steudel W.I. 1998. Faculty mentoring programme: ways of reducing anonymity. *Medical Education* 32: 441-443.
 34. Woessner R., Honold M., Stehr S.N., Steudel W.I. 2000. Support and faculty mentoring programs scheme. *Medical Education* 34: 635-641.

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